

EFFECT OF TAB DESIGN ON THE STRAIN DISTRIBUTION OF A BIAXIALLY LOADED CRUCIFORM COMPOSITE SPECIMEN

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SUMMARY

This paper focuses on the design of cruciform specimens for biaxial tensile testing. The strain fields of cruciform specimens with different claddings or tabs are analyzed both numerically and experimentally. The goal is to create a uniform strain field and thus reduce strain concentrations in the gage section of the specimen.

Keywords: In-plane Biaxial Testing, Specimen Design, Digital Image Correlation, Finite Element Analysis, Polymer Matrix Composites.

INTRODUCTION

In general, composite laminates are developing multiaxial stress states [1]. To get an accurate representation of the behaviour of composite materials in a structure, tests under a uniaxial stress state do not satisfy. Therefore biaxial testing has to be considered. Despite the large demand for this experimental biaxial information there is little existing experimental capability to evaluate the multi-axial response of composite materials [2].

The commonly used method to apply biaxial loads to a composite specimen is the combined torsion and tension/compression or pressure and tension/compression of a thin-walled tubular specimen. In real constructions, components in fibre reinforced composite materials are often made in the form of flat or gently curved panels. Consequently the biaxial behaviour of the tubes is different from the real behaviour. The most appropriate method for biaxial testing consists of applying in-plane biaxial loads to cruciform specimens. Therefore, a plane biaxial test device and a suitable cruciform specimen geometry have been developed at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel [3].

The developed specimen has an adapted fillet corner radius and a reduced thickness in the centre to ensure biaxial failure in the gage section. It fulfils the specific conditions necessary for a correct biaxial test. Nevertheless, there are still some strain concentrations present in the specimen [4]. In this paper it will be investigated if the specimen can be optimised, focussing on the specimen production method and the material layup. The aim is to simplify the manufacturing of the specimen and to achieve a strain field which is as uniform as possible.

BIAXIAL TESTING

Biaxial test device

Many techniques to produce biaxial stress states in a specimen can be distinguished [5]. The most realistic method for biaxial testing consists of applying in-plane biaxial loads to a cruciform specimen. The plane biaxial test rig shown in Figure 1 was developed at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel. It consists of four independent servo-hydraulic actuators with a capacity of 100kN in each perpendicular direction. The use of hydraulic actuators represents a very versatile technique for the application of the loads. When only one actuator per loading direction is used [6], the centre of the specimen will move. This causes a side bending of the specimen, which results in undesirable non-symmetric strains. Systems -like the one used by the authors- with four actuators [7] and a close-loop servo control using the measured loads as feedback system, allow the centre of the specimen to stand still.

As no cylinders with hydrostatic bearing were used, failure or slip in one arm of the specimen will result in sudden radial forces which could seriously damage the servo-hydraulic cylinders and load cells. To prevent this, hinges were used to connect the specimen to the load cells and the servo-hydraulic cylinders to the test frame. Using four hinges in each loading direction results in an unstable situation in compression and consequently only tension loads can be applied.

Fig.1 Biaxial test bench.

Fig.2 Cruciform specimen geometry.

Cruciform specimen design

Designing an appropriate specimen is probably the most difficult issue of biaxial testing. In order to achieve a successful biaxial test, the cruciform specimen has to fulfill some conditions: (i) specimen failure in the biaxially loaded test zone, (ii) minimization of the strain concentrations, (iii) maximization of the region of uniform biaxial strain, (iv) repeatable results [8]. Various specimen geometries have been compared by Smits et al [3] in order to obtain a proper cruciform specimen design. On the base of Finite Element (FE) analysis, completed with experimental results, the geometry in Figure 2 was developed. The specimen has a total length of 250 mm, an arm-width of 25 mm and a corner fillet radius of 6.25 mm. In the centre, material is milled away in the thickness direction to ensure biaxial failure.

Purpose of biaxial testing

The biaxial tests, accomplished in the past and present at the author's institution, have as main intention the strength and stiffness characterization of fibre reinforced

composite materials [9]. Both quasi-static and dynamic loading conditions are studied. The strength or failure characterization of the material is necessary to evaluate existing failure criteria. As the geometry of a biaxial specimen is complex compared to a uniaxial beam specimen, we cannot use the same simple analytical formulas to retrieve the present stresses as in a uniaxial test. The calculation of the stresses is not straightforward and consequently the importance of strain determination increases.

The stiffness determination is very important if we consider biaxial fatigue tests. As the mechanical material parameters cannot be obtained as with classical uniaxial tests, other identification methods have to be considered. An inverse method, which can be formulated as an optimization problem where the function to be minimized is an error function that expresses the difference between a numerical and an experimental strain field, was developed at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel [10]. In a first stage, the inverse method was developed to obtain the orthotropic elastic material parameters of a cruciform composite specimen under quasi-static loading. In a second stage, the method will be used in fatigue tests. These tests require a tool to study the degradation development of the orthotropic elastic parameters.

Measuring techniques

The calculation of the stress field of the cruciform specimen is not straightforward due to the uncertainty of the failure area size. Therefore, it is easier and more accurate to work with strains for the analysis of the experiment and the formulation of the failure envelopes. In order to get an idea of the surface strains of the whole specimen, full field measuring techniques instead of local techniques have to be used. In the author's work, the most frequently used technique is Digital Image Correlation (DIC), but also experiments using Electronic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (ESPI) were performed.

Fig.3 Principle of the Digital Image Correlation Technique.

DICT offers the possibility to determine displacement and deformation fields at the surface of objects under any kind of loading. Figure 3 depicts the working principle of the DICT. Pictures of an object on which a speckle pattern was applied, are taken at different loading steps and stored onto a computer through a framegrabber. The two images are compared by selecting an amount of neighbouring pixels (called subset) from the undeformed image and retrieving it in the deformed images. Subsequently, the corresponding displacement of the centre of the subset can be calculated. The calculation of the displacements of multiple subset centres yields the desired displacement field. The strain field is then calculated by numerical differentiation of the smoothed displacement field.

MILLING OR TABBING

Currently, the cruciform specimens are produced by manufacturing a plate with a thickness equal to the thickness of the arms and milling material away in the centre (Fig.4a). Using this technique, which we will call the milling-method, the gage section can get damaged if fibres are pulled out. A more secure production method can be the tabbing-method (Fig.4b). On the composite plate with the thickness of the central gauge section, the extra layers of the arms are glued on both sides. Consequently, there is no risk in damaging the central gauge section. On the other hand, bad adhesion of one of the layers can cause delaminations and improper failure modes of the specimen. Therefore, we will compare results obtained on specimens produced by the two methods.

Fig.4 Specimen production :
(a) milling or (b) tabbing.

Fig.5 5-element strain gage and corresponding DIC-zones on the other side of the specimen.

Test set-up

Two different composite materials were used in the context of this research. The first material tested is a glassfibre reinforced epoxy with a $[(\pm 45^\circ 0^\circ)_4 (\pm 45^\circ)]$ lay-up typical for wind turbine blades. The thickness of the arms and the central zone are respectively 6.57 mm and 3.59 mm (Fig.2a). The second tested material is carbon reinforced epoxy. To produce the specimens, carbon UD SE84 prepreg material was used in a $[(90/0)_2 (0/90)_2]_s$ lay-up. The thickness of each lamina is 0.28mm, which results in an arm thickness of 4.48 mm and a central thickness of 2.24 mm (Fig.2b).

For the specimens produced with the tabbing-method, cruciform plates without a hole and tabbing plates with a hole were manufactured. Before gluing the tabs, the plate surfaces were prepared properly.

Glass fibre reinforced epoxy specimens

To verify the influence of the adhesive, two different epoxy-glues are used. For one specimen, Araldite AW 106 with hardener HV953U was used. We will refer to it as adhesive A. For the other specimen, Epicote 828 LVEL with hardener Lab 2053 H was used. We will refer to it as adhesive E. The second adhesive was chosen because it is more ductile compared to adhesive A. Also, it is frequently used for gluing tabs to uniaxial specimens and it cures at room temperature.

For this analysis the loading ratio 3.85/1 was applied, i.e. a 3.85 times higher load is applied in the x direction as in the y direction. The specimens are observed by DIC to obtain the strain fields in every loading step. On the other side of the specimen, a uniaxial 5-element strain gage with elements of 1mm was glued to measure ε_x from the centre to the edge of the biaxially loaded zone (Fig.5). All these results are compared with earlier results of specimens produced by the milling-method.

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy specimens

The tests on carbon reinforced epoxy are carried out for different loading ratio's, namely 1/0, 1/1, 2/1 and 3/1. For each loading ratio, specimens were produced by the milling method as well as by the tabbing method. Only adhesive A was used to glue the tabs onto the specimens. DIC was applied for strain measuring. Also, FE simulations are carried out using a 3D finite element damage model of the milled specimen [11].

Results

Glass fibre reinforced epoxy specimens

In table 2, the failure loads and average strains at failure in the gauge section of the glassfibre reinforced epoxy specimens are summarised. It can be observed that the specimen with adhesive A obtains a higher failure load and failure strains ε_x compared to the specimen with adhesive E. Nevertheless, the values for both tabbed specimen are significantly lower as these for the milled specimen.

Fig.6 ε_x , ε_{xy} and ε_y fields for a (a) milled specimen, (b) tabbed specimen with adhesive A and (c) tabbed specimen with adhesive E at a load of 17.3 kN / 4.5 kN.

Figure 6 presents the ε_x , ε_{xy} and ε_y fields at a certain load (17.3 kN /4.5 kN) for the three specimens. Examining the ε_x field, one can notice that the strains in the gauge section for the tabbed specimens are a little bit higher compared to these of the milled specimen. Combined with the fact that in the arms in x-direction no or only low loads are present, it can be stated that the tabs are at this load already partly debonded. Most of the load is transferred through the middle layer in the cases (b) and (c) while in case (a) the total thickness of the arms is used to transfer the loads from the clamp to the central gauge section. The higher shear strains in the corners of the tabbed specimens are also related to this problem of debonding.

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy specimens

Fig.7 ε_x , ε_y and ε_{xy} fields for a (a) tabs, load ratio 1/0, (b) milled, load ratio 1/0, (c) FE, load ratio 1/0, (d) tabs, load ratio 3/1, (e) milled, load ratio 3/1, (f) FE, load ratio 3/1 at a load of 20 kN in x direction.

In table 1, the failure loads and average strains at failure in the gauge section of the carbon reinforced epoxy specimens are summarised. For all loading ratio's, the specimens produced with the milling method obtain higher failure loads compared to the specimens produced with the tabbing method. The tabbed specimens reach a failure load which is 4% (3/1 loading ratio) to 30% (1/0 loading ratio) lower as the failure load for the milled specimens.

Figure 7 presents the ϵ_x , ϵ_y and ϵ_{xy} fields at a certain load (20 kN in the x-direction) for the load ratios 1/0 (Fig.7 a, b and c) and 3/1 (Fig.7 d, e and f) for both milled and tabbed specimens. Additionally, numerically obtained strain fields for the same load cases are included. Similar things can be noticed as with the glassfibre epoxy specimens. There is no or only little strain in the upper layer of the tabbed specimen. Also, slightly higher strains are present in the centre of the tabbed specimen compared to the milled specimen. The strain fields of the FE-model and the milled specimen correspond well, since the numerical model does not take into account delaminations.

Table 1 Failure load and central failure strain for the tested carbon/epoxy specimens.

	Loading Ratio F_x / F_y	$F_{x, failure}$ [kN]	Dict _{,centre} $\epsilon_{x, failure}$ [%]	Dict _{,centre} $\epsilon_{y, failure}$ [%]
Milled	1/0	42.4	1.23	-0.07
	1/1	42.1	1.05	1.13
	2/1	44.4	1.20	0.54
	3/1	37.6	1.08	0.19
Adhesive A	1/0	29.5	1.35	-0.01
	1/1	34.1	0.85	0.90
	2/1	32.1	1.10	0.11
	3/1	36.1	1.07	0.36

Fig.8 Specimen failure : (top) glass/epoxy (bottom) carbon/epoxy.

Discussion

Using the tabbing method to produce the specimen in stead of the milling method results in much lower failure loads and lower strains at failure in the central gauge section. This is the result of premature failure of the tabs. Already at an early stage in the loading process, cracking of the specimen due to debonding of the tabs can be heard. When examining the tabbed specimens after failure, one can notice that the tabs are delaminated from the central layer (Fig.8). No fibres are pulled out of the laminates since failure occurred in the glue.

TAB LAY-UP EFFECT

In the previous section “*Milling or Tabbing*”, the layup of the glassfibre epoxy specimens remained in all cases $[(\pm 45^\circ \ 0^\circ)_4 (\pm 45^\circ)]$. With this layup, strain concentrations are present near the edges of the gauge section [12] (Fig.9). Between the

upper $\pm 45^\circ$ lamina of the central laminate and the lower 0° lamina of the tab interlaminar shear strains are present. These strains can cause delamination of the laminas.

Reversing the tab layout, in order to give the lower tab lamina the same $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation as the upper central lamina, reduces the interlaminar shear strains significantly. This was proven by a 3D finite element simulation. In Figure 10, one can notice that the strain concentrations in x-direction are reduced significantly by reversing the layout of the tabs. The efficiency of this intervention in practice will be examined in this section.

Fig.9 ϵ_x field of a biaxially loaded specimen (glass/epoxy) obtained with DIC and FEM

Fig.10 FE results of the ϵ_x field (upper central layer) with standard and reversed tab layout (glass/epoxy).

Test set-up

The influence of the tab layout on the strain field and on the failure loads was investigated on specimens manufactured using the tabbing method. Only the glass fibre reinforced epoxy material was used, with the same layout as in the previous section. Two specimens with reversed tab layout (further referred to as tabbing R) were manufactured, both with a different adhesive. The specimens were loaded until failure at a load ratio of 3.85/1. Strains are measured by strain gages and DIC. The results are compared with the previously obtained results for the standard layout, further referred to as tabbing N.

Results

Table 2 Failure load and average central failure strain (DIC and strain gages) for the tested glassfibre/epoxy specimens.

Adhesive	Tabbing	$F_{x, failure}$ [kN]	Dict _{,avg}	Dict _{,avg}	SG _{,avg}	SG _{,avg}
			$\epsilon_{x, failure}$ [%]	$\epsilon_{y, failure}$ [%]	$\epsilon_{x, failure}$ [%]	$\epsilon_{y, failure}$ [%]
Milled	N	44	2.09	-0.68	-	-
A	N	30.6	1.85	-0.66	1.82	-
A	R	33.7	1.89	-0.58	1.87	-
E	N	24.8	1.13	-0.47	-	-0.41
E	R	25.6	1.32	-0.40	1.39	-

The failure loads of all specimen, shown in table 2, can be compared. For both adhesives, higher failure loads are obtained for specimens with tabbing R compared to

specimens with tabbing N. Also for the failure strains in x direction, higher values are obtained with the reversed tabbing. Although the failure loads and the strains in the central gauge section of the specimen are closer to these obtained by the milled specimens, there is still a big difference between milled and tabbed specimens.

As an additional investigation, the strains obtained by strain gages can be compared with the strains obtained by DIC. In table 2, one can already notice the good agreement between the two measuring methods for the average strain measurements. When we compare the separate strain measurements at the 5 strain gage locations (Fig.11 and Fig.12), we can observe that the two strain measuring techniques correspond well. In the centre, slightly higher ϵ_x strains are present as near the edge, which is a good result considering that biaxial failure has to occur in the centre. It also points out the efficiency of the reversed tab layup, since with tabbing N ϵ_x was higher near the edge compared to the centre of the biaxial zone.

Fig.11 Force in the x-direction versus strain in the x-direction. Specimen with tabbing R and adhesive A.

Fig. 12 Force in the x-direction versus strain in the y-direction. Specimen with tabbing N and adhesive E.

Discussion

Using a reversed tabbing layup proves his benefit in higher failure loads and higher strains at failure. The tabs debond in a later stage in the loading process compared to the standard tab layup. This can be validated by DIC measurements. Also, the cracking sounds of debonding tabs are noticed at higher loads.

CONCLUSIONS

The design of a suitable specimen for in-plane biaxial testing is not straightforward. Some conditions, like failure in the biaxially loaded central zone of the specimen, have to be fulfilled. A proper specimen with reduced central thickness and an adapted corner fillet radius was developed at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel.

In order to optimise the specimen production method, results obtained on specimens produced by a milling method were compared with results obtained on specimens produced by using tabs. Problems occurred with the tabbing method in the form of debonding of the tabs. Consequently, lower failure loads were obtained and failure did not occur in the biaxially loaded central zone. Additional studies on the adhesion of the glue on the glassfibre epoxy laminate surface are necessary.

In order to reduce strain concentrations which are present at the edges of the central gauge area, the use of a reversed tabbing layup was investigated. Interlaminar shear strains between the upper lamina of the central area ($\pm 45^\circ$) and the lower lamina of the tab (0°) case ϵ_x strain concentrations. It was proven numerically and experimentally that these concentrations are reduced significantly by reversing the tab layup. Consequently, higher failure loads are obtained.

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References

1. W.P. Lin, H.T. Hu, Parametric study of failure stresses in fibre reinforced composite laminates subjected to biaxial tensile load, *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol 36 (12), 1481-1504, 2002.
2. P.D. Soden, M.J. Hinton, A.S. Kaddour, Biaxial test results for strength and deformation of a range of E-glass and carbon fibre reinforced composite laminates : failure exercise benchmark data, *Composites Science and Technology*, vol 62 (12), 1489-1514, 2002.
3. A. Smits, D. Van Hemelrijck, T.P. Philippidis, A. Cardon, Design of a cruciform specimen for biaxial testing of fibre reinforced composite laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*, vol 66 (7-8), 964-975, 2006.
4. C. Ramault, A. Makris, D. Van Hemelrijck, E. Lamkanfi, W. Van Paepegem, Strain Distribution in a Biaxially Loaded Cruciform Composite Specimen, *Proceedings of the 13th European Conference on Composite Materials*, Stockholm, Sweden, 2008.
5. A. Makris, C. Ramault, A. Smits, D. Van Hemelrijck, A. Clarke, C. Williamson, M. Gower, R. Shaw, R. Mera, E. Lamkanfi, W. Van Paepegem, A review of biaxial test methods for composites, *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Experimental Mechanics*, Alexandroupolis, Greece, 2007.
6. M. Chaudonneret, P. Gilles, R. Labourdette, H. Policella, Machine d'essais de traction biaxiale pour essais statiques et dynamiques, *La Recherche Aérospatiale*, 5, 299-305, 1977.
7. A. Makinde, L. Thibodeau, K.W. Neale, Development of an apparatus for biaxial testing using cruciform specimens, *Experimental Mechanics*, vol 32 (2), 138-44, 1992.
8. J.P. Boehler, S. Demmerle, S. Koss, A new direct biaxial testing machine for anisotropic materials, *Experimental Mechanics*, vol 34 (1), 1-9, 1994.

9. D. Van Hemelrijck, A. Makris, C. Ramault, E. Lamkanfi, W. Van Paepegem, D. Lecompte, Biaxial testing of fibre reinforced composite laminates, IMECHE Part L J. of Materials : Design and Applications, vol 222 (4), 231-239, 2008.
10. D. Lecompte, A. Smits, H. Sol, J. Vantomme, D. Van Hemelrijck, Mixed Numerical-Experimental technique for orthotropic parameter identification using biaxial tensile tests on cruciform specimens, International Journal of Solids and Structures, vol 44 (5), 1628-1642, 2007.
11. A. Makris, C. Ramault, D. Van Hemelrijck, E. Lamkanfi, W. Van Paepegem, Damage evolution of composite cruciform specimens under quasi-static biaxial loading, Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Composite Materials, Edinburgh, UK, 2009.
12. E. Lamkanfi, W. Van Paepegem, J. Degrieck, A. Makris, C. Ramault, D. Van Hemelrijck, Geometrical influence on the strain distribution in biaxial composite specimens, Proceedings of the 13th European Conference on Composite Materials, Stockholm, Sweden, 2008.